

to GA₃ at the seedling stage also produced endosperm sensitive to GA₃. Endosperm can therefore be used to rapidly identify genotypes that are sensitive to GA₃ with regard to height. ■

Effect of GA₃ on inducing α-amylase in endosperms.

Breeding methods

Identification of stable cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines for hybrid rice breeding in subhumid tropics

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Environmental factors influence stability of a CMS line. We need to identify suitable lines for developing hybrids adapted to western UP conditions. We evaluated eight CMS lines with wild abortive cytoplasm during 1990 wet season (WS) in a replicated experiment (Table 1).

Analysis of variance indicated significant differences among the CMS lines for seven characters. The lines generally are early flowering, have shorter plant stature, and have more tillers than their respective maintainer lines. CMS lines IR54752 A, IR54753 A, Pragathi, and Pushpa had fertile pollens and long duration and therefore are unstable. Lines IR46829 A, IR54754 A, IR54758 A, and V20 A had complete pollen sterility and did not set any seed in bagged panicles (Table 2). Spikelet fertility was 0.0, 2.7, 11.4, and 17.7%, respectively, for the lines under unbagged conditions. V20 A and IR54758 A had reasonably good seed set under these conditions, indicating better outcrossing

potential, possibly due to their floral traits favoring cross pollination.

Lines possessed early (V20 A) to mid-late (IR46829 A, IR54758 A, and IR54754 A) duration, nonlodging dwarf (V20 A, IR56829 A) or semidwarf (IR54754 A and IR54758 A) plant types, high to moderate tillering capacity, and larger sink size.

Overall comparative performance suggests V20 A and IR54758 A are the most suitable CMS lines because they possess complete stability for pollen sterility, better outcrossing potential under natural conditions, and several desirable plant features under WS conditions of UP. They are being exploited to develop hybrids. ■

Table 1. Analysis of variance of CMS lines for several characters. ^a Western Uttar Pradesh, India, 1990 WS.

Source of variance	Degrees of freedom	Mean square						
		Days to 50% flowering	Plant height	Number of effective tillers	Panicle length	Number of spikelets/panicle	Percent fertile spikelets	Percent pollen fertility
Replication	1	18.06	29.17	59.29	20.70	87.59	0.66	91.20
Genotype	7	399.41**	397.14**	45.39*	17.32*	2819.94*	461.41**	854.33**
Error	7	5.49	26.37	8.75	2.31	594.86	19.64	32.52
CV (%)		2.2	5.3	27.7	6.3	13.8	22.8	36.6

* and ** = significant at 5 and 1% level, respectively.

Table 2. Mean performance of CMS lines for some agronomic characters.^a Western Uttar Pradesh, India, 1990 WS.

CMS line	Days to 50% flowering		Plant height (cm)		Tillers (no.)		Panicle length (cm)		Pollen fertility (%)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)		Fertile spikelets (%)		
	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	A	B	Unbagged		Bagged
												A	B	A
IR46829	105.0	96.0	81.3	94.8	7.3	13.3	20.0	21.8	0.0	117.2	102.3	0.0	70.5	0.0
IR54752	118.0	117.0	102.0	104.8	10.3	11.4	25.2	28.3	10.3	191.6	194.5	20.0	48.2	18.5
IR54753	117.0	109.0	120.0	110.5	9.0	11.1	27.6	28.0	31.0	164.1	219.5	39.9	57.4	30.2
IR54754	110.0	101.0	90.3	98.0	9.8	11.0	23.8	25.6	0.0	189.9	163.7	2.7	63.8	0.0
IR54758	109.0	106.0	100.5	110.8	9.6	8.2	22.2	26.6	0.0	186.0	180.9	11.4	57.7	0.0
Pragathi	109.0	102.0	105.4	98.7	7.7	10.8	26.3	24.7	43.6	217.6	151.4	23.3	50.5	20.5
Pushpa	121.0	115.5	97.4	104.5	9.7	12.7	27.7	29.0	46.8	217.6	201.1	40.8	51.7	35.6
V20	76.0	69.0	75.0	81.1	22.2	9.0	21.1	2.1	0.0	128.3	93.2	17.7	72.8	0.0
Mean	108.2	102.0	96.6	100.4	10.7	10.9	24.2	25.7	16.4	176.3	163.2	19.5	59.2	13.1
LSD (0.05)	5.5	4.1	12.1	3.5	7.0	6.6	3.5	2.3	13.4	57.6	35.0	10.4	12.9	13.2
LSD (0.01)	8.2	6.0	17.9	5.1	10.3	9.7	5.3	3.4	19.9	85.1	51.7	15.4	19.1	18.6

^aA = CMS line, B = maintainer of CMS line (A).

Using potassium chlorate (KClO₃) to distinguish indica-japonica hybrids from indica and japonica parents

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Phenol reaction of the hull can be used to distinguish indica from japonica varieties but not indica-japonica hybrids from their parents because the hybrids show a positive reaction as indicas. We tested whether the multigenic inheritance for KClO₃ tolerance in rice seedlings can be used to distinguish indica-japonica hybrids from their parents.

We soaked 100 seedlings with plumules of 0.5-1.0 cm for each of six indica-japonica hybrids (F₁) and their parents in 1% KClO₃ solution for 24 h, then washed and stored them at 30 °C for 4-5 d. The experiment was replicated twice. Degree of KClO₃ injury for each seedling was scored on a scale of 0-3 (see table). Percentage of seedlings injured was estimated using injury index:

$$\text{Injury index} = \frac{\sum (\text{score} \times \text{seedling no.})}{\text{the largest score} \times \text{total seedling no.}}$$

Reaction score and injury index of hybrid and parent rice seedlings after KClO₃ treatment.

Hybrid or parent	Seedlings (no.)	Seedlings (no.) with given reaction score ^a				Injury index ^b (%)
		0	1	2	3	
<i>Indica</i>						
CE 64	203			53	150	91.3 a
Xiangai	200			74	126	87.7 a
Ks-9	200			27	173	95.5 a
w6154s	208			118	90	81.1 a
<i>Hybrid</i>						
Ce 64/02428	201		110	83	8	45.7 b
Xiangai/02428	197		159	33	5	40.6 b
Ks-9/029	208		117	91	3	49.4 b
w6154s/02428	200		156	39	5	41.5 b
w6154s/029	198		130	67	1	44.9 b
Ce 64/029	205		145	56	4	45.7 b
<i>Japonica</i>						
02428	200	200				0 c
029	200	200				0 c

^a0 = normal growth without any injury, 1 = partial chlorosis at the margin of the first euphyllum, 2 = yellowing with partial rolling of the first euphyllum, 3 = withering of whole seedling. ^bIn a column, values followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 1% level.

Analysis of variance with a complete random design was used to test for significant differences.

The three seedling types differed distinctly in their tolerance for KClO₃.

Japonica parents were tolerant of KClO₃ and indica parents sensitive. Most of the hybrids reacted moderately, giving an injury index (40-50%) intermediate

between their indica and japonica parents.

Results suggest that tolerance of seedlings for KClO₃ can be used to test whether the type is a true hybrid or a pure indica or japonica. ■